

AGENT ENABLED MINING OF DISTRIBUTED PROTEIN DATA BANKS

G. S. Bhamra¹, A. K. Verma² and R. B. Patel³

¹M. M. University, Mullana, Haryana, 133207 - India

²Thapar University, Patiala, Punjab, 147004- India

³Chandigarh College of Engineering & Technology, Chandigarh- 160019- India

ABSTRACT

Mining biological data is an emergent area at the intersection between bioinformatics and data mining (DM). The intelligent agent based model is a popular approach in constructing Distributed Data Mining (DDM) systems to address scalable mining over large scale distributed data. The nature of associations between different amino acids in proteins has also been a subject of great anxiety. There is a strong need to develop new models and exploit and analyze the available distributed biological data sources. In this study, we have designed and implemented a multi-agent system (MAS) called Agent enriched Quantitative Association Rules Mining for Amino Acids in distributed Protein Data Banks (AeQARM-AAPDB). Such globally strong association rules enhance understanding of protein composition and are desirable for synthesis of artificial proteins. A real protein data bank is used to validate the system.

KEYWORDS

Knowledge Discovery, Association Rules, Intelligent Agents, Multi-Agent System, Bioinformatics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Data Mining (DM) is a process to automatically extract some interesting and valid data patterns or trends representing knowledge, implicitly stored in large databases [1], [2]. Distributed Data Mining (DDM) is concerned with application of classical DM procedures in a distributed computing environment trying to make the best of the available resources. In DDM, DM takes place both locally at each geographically distributed site and at a global level where the local knowledge is merged in order to discover global knowledge. A DDM system is a very complex entity that is comprised of many components; mining algorithms; communication subsystems; resources management; task scheduling; user interface etc. It should provide efficient access to both distributed data and computing resources; monitor the entire mining procedure; and present results to users in appropriate formats. A successful DDM system is also flexible enough to adapt to various situations [3], [4], [5], [6], [7].

Intelligent software agent technology is an interdisciplinary technology. The motivating idea of this technology is the development and efficient utilization of autonomous software objects called agents, which have access to geographically distributed and heterogeneous information resources to simplify the complexities of distributed computing. They are autonomous, adaptive, reactive, pro-active, social, cooperative, collaborative and flexible. They also support temporal continuity and mobility within the network. An intelligent agent with mobility feature is known as Mobile Agent (MA). MA migrates from node to node in a heterogeneous network without losing its operability. It can continue to function even if the user is disconnected from the network. On reaching at a node MA is delivered to an Agent Execution Environment (AEE) where its executable parts are started running. Upon completion of the desired task, it delivers the results to

the home node. With MA, a single serialized object is transmitted over the network carrying the small amount of resultant data only thus reducing the consumption of network bandwidth, latency (response time delay) and network traffic. An AEE or Mobile Agent Platform (MAP), is server application that provides the appropriate functionality to MAs to authenticate, execute, communicate (with other agents, users, and other platforms), migrate to other platform, and use system resources in a secure way. A Multi Agent System (MAS) is distributed application comprised of multiple interacting intelligent agent components [8].

Table 1. Single Letter codes for Amino Acids

Sr. No.	Amino Acid Name	Single Letter Code	Three Letter Code
1	Alanine	A	Ala
2	Cysteine	C	Cys
3	Aspartic Acid	D	Asp
4	Glutamic Acid	E	Glu
5	Phenylalanine	F	Phe
6	Glycine	G	Gly
7	Histidine	H	His
8	Isoleucine	I	Ile
9	Lysine	K	Lys
10	Leucine	L	Leu
11	Methionine	M	Met
12	Asparagine	N	Asn
13	Proline	P	Pro
14	Glutamine	Q	Gln
15	Arginine	R	Arg
16	Serine	S	Ser
17	Threonine	T	Thr
18	Valine	V	Val
19	Tryptophan	W	Trp
20	Tyrosine	Y	Tyr

Bioinformatics or computational molecular biology aims at automated analysis and the management of high-throughput biological data as well as modelling and simulation of complex biological systems. Bioinformatics has very much changed since the first sequence alignment algorithms in 1970s [9]. Today in-silico analysis is a fundamental component of biomedical research. Bioinformatics has now encompasses a wide range of subject areas from structural biology, genomics to gene expression studies [10], [11]. The post-genomic era has resulted into availability of the enormous amount of distributed biological data sets that require suitable tools and methods for modelling and analyzing biological processes and sequences. The bioinformatics research community feels a strong need to develop new models and exploit and analyze the available genomes [12]. The protein sequences are made up of 20 types of Amino Acids (AA). Each AA is represented by a single letter alphabet as shown in Table 1. Unique 3-dimensional structure of each protein is decided completely by its amino-acid sequence. Proteins are important constituents of cellular machinery of any organism and the functioning of proteins heavily depends upon its AA sequence. A slight change in the sequence might completely change the functioning of the protein. Therefore, the nature of associations between different amino acids has been a subject of great anxiety. In [20], authors mine the association rules among amino acids in protein sequences. As per the literature available, no researcher has applied the agent technology to mine association rules for amino acids from distributed protein data sets. The amalgamation of

the DDM and MAS provides rewarding solution in terms of security, scalability, storage cost, computation cost and communication cost. Mining biological data is an emerging area and continues to be an extremely important problem, both for DM and for biological sciences [21]. State of the art in use of agent technology in bioinformatics is reviewed in [22].

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 discusses the distributed association rule mining and preliminary notations used in this paper. A running environment for the proposed system is present in Section 3 along with algorithms used for various components and protein data banks used in this study. The layout and working of various agents involved in the proposed system and their algorithms are also discussed. System is implemented in Java and its performance is studied in Section 4 and finally the article is concluded in Section 5.

2. DISTRIBUTED ASSOCIATION RULE MINING

Let $DB = \{T_j, j = 1 \dots D\}$ be a transactional dataset of size D where each transaction T is assigned an identifier (TID) and $I = \{d_i, i = 1 \dots m\}$, total m data items in DB . A set of items in a particular transaction T is called itemset or pattern. An itemset, $P = \{d_i, i = 1 \dots k\}$, which is a set of k data items in a particular transaction T and $P \subseteq I$, is called k-itemset. Support of an itemset, $s(P) = \frac{\text{No_of_T_containing_P}}{D} \%$ is the frequency of occurrence of itemset P in DB , where $\text{No_of_T_containing_P}$ is the support count (sup_count) of itemset P . Frequent Itemsets (FIs) are the itemset that appear in DB frequently, i.e., if $s(P) \geq \text{min_th_sup}$ (given minimum threshold support), then P is a frequent k-itemset. Finding such FIs plays an essential role in mining the interesting relationships among itemsets. Frequent Itemset Mining (FIM) is the task of finding the set of all the subsets of FIs in a transactional database. It is CPU and input/output intensive task, mainly because of the large size of the datasets involved [2].

Association Rules (ARs) first introduced in [13], are used to discover the associations (or co-occurrences) among item in a database. AR is an implication of the form $P \Rightarrow Q$ [support, confidence] where, $P \subset I, Q \subset I$ and P and Q are disjoint itemsets, i.e., $P \cap Q = \emptyset$. An AR is measured in terms of its support (s) and confidence (c) factors. An AR $P \Rightarrow Q$ is said to be strong if $s(P \Rightarrow Q) \geq \text{min_th_sup}$ (given minimum threshold support) and $c(P) \geq \text{min_th_conf}$ (given minimum threshold confidence). Association Rule Mining (ARM) today is one of the most important aspects of DM tasks. In ARM all the strong ARs are generated from the FIs. The ARM can be viewed as two step process [14], [15].

1. Find all the frequent k-itemsets (L_k)
2. Generate Strong ARs from L_k
 - a. For each frequent itemset, $l \in L_k$, generate all non empty subsets of l .
 - b. For every non empty subset s of l , output the rule " $s \Rightarrow (l-s)$ ", if $\frac{\text{sup_count}(l)}{\text{sup_count}(s)} \geq \text{min_th_conf}$

Distributed Association Rule Mining (DARM) generates the globally strong association rules from the global FIs in a distributed environment. Because of an intrinsic data skew property of the distributed database, it is desirable to mine the global rules for the global business decisions and

the local rules for the local business decisions. Comparative analysis of existing agent based DARM systems can be found in [23].

Few preliminaries notations and definitions required for defining DARM and to make this study self contained are as follows:

- $S = \{S_i, i = 1 \dots n\}$, n distributed sites.
- $S_{CENTRAL}$, Central Site.
- $PDB_i = \{PR_m, m = 1 \dots X_i\}$, Protein Data Bank of X_i protein records at site S_i , each PR_m has two main parts; first part is the description headers (PD) for structural classification of protein and the second part contains protein sequence (PS), i.e., the chain of amino acids. Snapshot of PDB_i is shown in Appendix A.1.
- $FPDB_i = \{PR_k, k = 1 \dots D_i\}$, Filtered Protein Data Bank of D_i protein records at site S_i , where length of PS in each PR is in the range ≥ 50 and < 400 . Snapshot of $FPDB_i$ is shown in Appendix A.2.
- AAF_i , Data bank of amino acids frequency for each $PR \in FPDB$ at site S_i . AAF_1 is shown in Appendix A.3. AAF_2 and AAF_3 are not shown due to space constraint.
- BDB_i , Boolean Data Bank that contains a value '1' if the frequency of an amino acid lies in the specific range and '0' otherwise at site S_i . Snapshot of BDB_i is shown in Appendix A.5.
- IDB_i , Itemset Data Bank of frequency partition items to map boolean value '1' with its frequency partition item number at site S_i . Snapshot of IDB_i is shown in Appendix A.6.
- $L_{k(i)}^{FI}$, Local frequent k-itemsets at site S_i .
- $L_{k(i)}^{FISC}$, List of support count $\forall Itemset \in L_{k(i)}^{FI}$.
- L_i^{LSAR} , List of locally strong association rules at site S_i .
- $L^{TLSAR} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n L_i^{LSAR}$, List of total locally strong association rules.
- $L_k^{TFI} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n L_{k(i)}^{FI}$, List of total frequent k-itemsets.
- $L_k^{GFI} = \bigcap_{i=1}^n L_{k(i)}^{FI}$, List of global frequent k-itemsets.
- $L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR}$, List of Globally strong association rule.

Local Knowledge Base (LKB), at site S_i , comprises of $L_{k(i)}^{FI}$, $L_{k(i)}^{FISC}$ and L_i^{LSAR} which can provide reference to the local supervisor for local decisions. Global Knowledge Base (GKB), at $S_{CENTRAL}$, comprises of L^{TLSAR} , L_k^{TFI} , L_k^{GFI} and $L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR}$ for the global decision making. Like ARM, DARM task can also be viewed as two-step process [15]:

1. Find the global frequent k-itemset (L_k^{GFI}) from the distributed Local frequent k-itemsets ($L_{k(i)}^{FI}$) from the partitioned datasets.
2. Generate globally strong association rules ($L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR}$) from L_k^{GFI} .

3. PROPOSED AEQARM-AAPDB SYSTEM

3.1. Environment for the proposed system

Every MAS needs an underlying AEE to provide running infrastructure on which agents can be deployed and tested. A running environment has been designed in Java to execute all the DM agents involved in the proposed system. Various attributes of the MA are encapsulated within a data structure known as *AgentProfile*. *AgentProfile* contains the name of MA (*AgentName*), version number (*AgentVersion*), entire byte code (*BC*), list of nodes to be visited by MA, i.e., itinerary plan (L^{NODES}), type of the itinerary (*ItinType*) which can be serial or parallel, a reference of current execution state (*AObject*) and an additional data structure known as *Briefcase* that acts as a result bag of MA to store final resultant knowledge ($Result_{S_i}$) at a particular site. Computational time (*CPUTime*) taken by a MA at a particular site is also stored in $Result_{S_i}$. In addition to results, *Briefcase* also contains the system time for start of agent journey ($TripTime_{start}$), system time for end of journey ($TripTime_{end}$) and total round trip time of MA ($TripTime$) calculated using the formula $TripTime \leftarrow TripTime_{end} - TripTime_{start}$. This environment consists of the following three components:

- **Data Mining Agent Execution Environment (DM_AEE):** It is the key component that acts as a Server. DM_AEE is deployed on any distributed sites S_i and is responsible for receiving, executing and migrating all the visiting data mining (DM) agents. It receives the incoming *AgentProfile* at site S_i , retrieves the entire *BC* of agent and save it with *AgentName.class* in the local file system of the site S_i after that execution of the agent is started using *AObject*. Steps are shown in Algorithm 1.
- **Agent Launcher (AL):** It acts a Client at agent launching station ($S_{CENTRAL}$) and launches the goal oriented DM agents on behalf of the user through a user interface to the DM_AEE running at the distributed sites. Agent Pool (or Zone) at $S_{CENTRAL}$ is a repository of all mobile as well as stationary agents (SAs). AL first reads and stores *AgentName* in *AgentProfile*. The entire *BC* of the *AgentName* is loaded from the Agent Pool and stored in *AgentProfile*. L^{NODES} and *ItinType* are retrieved and stored in *AgentProfile*. $TripTime_{start}$ is maintained in *Briefcase* which is further added to *AgentProfile*. In case of parallel computing model, i.e., if *ItinType* = *Parallel* AL creates L^{NODES} number of clones of the specific MA and dispatches each clone in parallel to all the sites listed in L^{NODES} . Here L^{NODES} number of threads are created to dispatch the MAs in parallel. Each clone has *AgentVersion* starting from 1 to size of L^{NODES} , which is used to identify each clone on the network. Before dispatching the clone of a MA to DM_AEE, the current state of the newly created *i*th clone object (*AObject*[*i*]) is also stored in *AgentProfile*. AL also contacts the Result Manager (RM) for processing the *Briefcase* of an agent. Detailed steps are given in Algorithm 2.
- **Result Manager (RM):** It manages and processes the *Briefcase* of all MAs. RM is either contacted by a MA for submitting its results or by AL for processing the results of the specific MA. On completion of itinerary, each DM agent submits its results to RM which computes total round trip time ($TripTime$) of that MA and saves it in the *Briefcase* of that agent. If *ItinType* = *Parallel* then it saves the *AgentProfile* of all the clones of the agent with *AgentName* in a collection $L^{AllProfiles}_{AgentName}$. It is assumed that all the clones report

their results to RM. RM may be equipped with the feature of non reporting clones by issuing an alert to AL for that clone with specific *AgentVersion*. AL then launch a new clone for the specific *AgentVersion* for the specific site. When it is contacted by AL for processing the results of a specific agent it sends back a collection $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$ for all the clones of that agent. Steps are defined in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 1 DATA MINING AGENT EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT (DM_AEE)

```

1: procedure DM_AEE( )
2: while TRUE do
3:   AgentProfile  $\leftarrow$  listen and receive AgentProfile at  $S_i$ 
4:   AgentName  $\leftarrow$  get AgentName from AgentProfile
5:   BC  $\leftarrow$  retrieve the BC of agent from AgentProfile
6:   save the BC with AgentName.class in the local file system of  $S_i$ 
7:   AObject  $\leftarrow$  get AObject from AgentProfile ▷ current state
8:   AObject.run() ▷ start executing mobile agent
9: end while
10: end procedure

```

Algorithm 2 AGENT LAUNCHER (AL) FOR AEQARM-AAPDB

```

1: procedure AL( )
2: option  $\leftarrow$  read option (dispatch / result)
3: switch option do
4:   case dispatch ▷ dispatch the mobile agent to DM_AEE
5:     AgentName  $\leftarrow$  read Mobile Agent's name
6:     BC  $\leftarrow$  load entire byte code of AgentName from AgentPool
7:     add AgentName and BC to AgentProfile
8:      $L^{NODES} \leftarrow$  read Itinerary (IP addresses) of mobile agent
9:     ItinType  $\leftarrow$  read ItinType ( Serial / Parallel)
10:    add ItinType to AgentProfile
11:    if ItinType = "Parallel" then ▷ Parallel Itinerary
12:      AObject[ $L^{NODES}.size$ ] ▷ Array of Agent Objects for clone references
13:      TripTime_{start}  $\leftarrow$  get system time for start of the agent journey
14:      add TripTime_{start} to Briefcase
15:      add Briefcase to AgentProfile
16:      switch AgentName do
17:        case PDBFA
18:          for  $i \leftarrow 1, L^{NODES}.size$  do ▷ for each node in the itinerary
19:            AgentVersion  $\leftarrow$   $i$ 
20:            add AgentVersion to AgentProfile
21:            NodeAddress  $\leftarrow$   $L^{NODES}.get(i)$  ▷ get an IP address
22:            AObject[ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow$  new PDBFA(AgentProfile)
23:            Add AObject[ $i$ ] to AgentProfile ▷ clone's state
24:            Transfer AgentProfile to DM_AEE at NodeAddress
25:          end for

```

```

26:     end case
27:     case AAFFA
28:         for  $i \leftarrow 1, L^{NODES}.size$  do                                ▷ for each node in the itinerary
29:             AgentVersion  $\leftarrow i$ 
30:             add AgentVersion to AgentProfile
31:             NodeAddress  $\leftarrow L^{NODES}.get(i)$                             ▷ get an IP address
32:             AObject[ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow new AAFFA(AgentProfile)$ 
33:             Add AObject[ $i$ ] to AgentProfile                                ▷ clone's state
34:             Transfer AgentProfile to DM_AEE at NodeAddress
35:         end for
36:     end case
37:     case FMIDBGA
38:         max_freq  $\leftarrow read\ maximum\ frequency\ range\ for\ amino\ acids$ 
39:         for  $i \leftarrow 1, L^{NODES}.size$  do                                ▷ for each node in the itinerary
40:             AgentVersion  $\leftarrow i$ 
41:             add AgentVersion to AgentProfile
42:             NodeAddress  $\leftarrow L^{NODES}.get(i)$                             ▷ get an IP address
43:             AObject[ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow new FMIDBGA(AgentProfile, max\_freq)$ 
44:             Add AObject[ $i$ ] to AgentProfile                                ▷ clone's state
45:             Transfer AgentProfile to DM_AEE at NodeAddress
46:         end for
47:     end case
48:     case LKGA_P
49:         min_s  $\leftarrow read\ minimum\ threshold\ support$ 
50:         min_c  $\leftarrow read\ minimum\ threshold\ confidence$ 
51:         for  $i \leftarrow 1, L^{NODES}.size$  do                                ▷ for each node in the itinerary
52:             AgentVersion  $\leftarrow i$ 
53:             add AgentVersion to AgentProfile
54:             NodeAddress  $\leftarrow L^{NODES}.get(i)$                             ▷ get an IP address
55:             AObject[ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow new LKGA_P(AgentProfile, min\_s, min\_c)$ 
56:             Add AObject[ $i$ ] to AgentProfile                                ▷ clone's state
57:             Transfer AgentProfile to DM_AEE at NodeAddress
58:         end for
59:     end case
60:     case LKCA_P
61:         for  $i \leftarrow 1, L^{NODES}.size$  do                                ▷ for each node in the itinerary
62:             AgentVersion  $\leftarrow i$ 
63:             add AgentVersion to AgentProfile
64:             NodeAddress  $\leftarrow L^{NODES}.get(i)$                             ▷ get an IP address
65:             AObject[ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow new LKCA_P(AgentProfile)$ 
66:             Add AObject[ $i$ ] to AgentProfile                                ▷ clone's state
67:             Transfer AgentProfile to DM_AEE at NodeAddress
68:         end for
69:     end case
70:     case GKDA_P
71:          $L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR} \leftarrow load\ L_{CENTRAL}^{CENTRAL}$  generated by GKGA at  $S_{CENTRAL}$ 

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72:         add  $L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR}$  to Briefcase
73:         add updated Briefcase to AgentProfile
74:         for  $i \leftarrow 1, L^{NODES}.size$  do                                     ▷ for each node in the itinerary
75:             AgentVersion  $\leftarrow i$ 
76:             add AgentVersion to AgentProfile
77:             NodeAddress  $\leftarrow L^{NODES}.get(i)$                                ▷ get an IP address
78:             AObject[i]  $\leftarrow new GKDA\_P(AgentProfile)$ 
79:             Add AObject[i] to AgentProfile                                     ▷ clone's state
80:             Transfer AgentProfile to DM_AEE at NodeAddress
81:         end for
82:     end case
83: end switch
84: end if
85: end case
86: case result                                                                ▷ process the results of mobile agent
87:     AgentName  $\leftarrow read\ mobile\ agent's\ name$ 
88:     ItinType  $\leftarrow read\ mobile\ agent's\ itinerary\ type$ 
89:     add AgentName and ItinType to  $L^{AgentInfo}$ 
90:     if ItinType = " Parallel" then
91:          $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfile} \leftarrow contact\ RM\ for\ L^{AgentInfo}$ 
92:         switch AgentName do
93:             case PDBFA
94:                 for all AgentProfile  $\in L_{AgentName}^{AllProfile}$  do                 ▷ for each clone
95:                     Briefcase  $\leftarrow retrieve\ Briefcase\ from\ AgentProfile$ 
96:                     process the Briefcase of PDBFA clone
97:                 end for
98:             end case
99:             case AAFFA
100:                for all AgentProfile  $\in L_{AgentName}^{AllProfile}$  do                 ▷ for each clone
101:                    Briefcase  $\leftarrow retrieve\ Briefcase\ from\ AgentProfile$ 
102:                    process the Briefcase of AAFFA clone
103:                end for
104:            end case
105:            case FMIDBGA
106:                for all AgentProfile  $\in L_{AgentName}^{AllProfile}$  do                 ▷ for each clone
107:                    Briefcase  $\leftarrow retrieve\ Briefcase\ from\ AgentProfile$ 
108:                    process the Briefcase of FMIDBGA clone
109:                end for
110:            end case
111:            case LKGA_P
112:                for all AgentProfile  $\in L_{AgentName}^{AllProfile}$  do                 ▷ for each clone
113:                    Briefcase  $\leftarrow retrieve\ Briefcase\ from\ AgentProfile$ 
114:                    process the Briefcase of LKGA_P clone
115:                end for
116:            end case
117:            case LKCA_P
118:                call RIGKGA( $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfile}$ )                               ▷ stationary agent

```

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119:         end case
120:         case GKDA_P
121:             for all AgentProfile  $\in L_{AgentName}^{AllProfile}$  do ▷ for each clone
122:                 Briefcase  $\leftarrow$  retrieve Briefcase from AgentProfile
123:                 process the Briefcase of GKDA_P clone
124:             end for
125:         end case
126:     end switch
127: end if
128: end case
129: end switch
130: end procedure

```

Algorithm 3 RESULT MANAGER(RM)

```

1: procedure RM()
2: while TRUE do
3:     listen and receive the incoming request
4:     if contacted by a mobile agent for submitting results from site  $S_i$  then
5:         AgentProfile  $\leftarrow$  receive the incoming AgentProfile from site  $S_i$ 
6:         ItinType  $\leftarrow$  retrieve ItinType from AgentProfile
7:         Briefcase  $\leftarrow$  retrieve mobile agent's Briefcase from AgentProfile
8:         TripTimestart  $\leftarrow$  retrieve TripTimestart from Briefcase
9:         TripTimeend  $\leftarrow$  retrieve TripTimeend from Briefcase
10:        TripTime  $\leftarrow$  TripTimeend - TripTimestart
11:        add TripTime to Briefcase
12:        add updated Briefcase to AgentProfile
13:        if ItinType = "Parallel" then
14:            AgentName  $\leftarrow$  retrieve AgentName from AgentProfile
15:            AgentVersion  $\leftarrow$  retrieve AgentVersion from AgentProfile
16:            if AgentVersion = 1 then
17:                add AgentProfile to  $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$ 
18:                save  $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$  at  $S_{CENTRAL}$ 
19:            end if
20:            if AgentVersion > 1 then
21:                retrieve  $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$  from  $S_{CENTRAL}$ 
22:                add AgentProfile to  $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$ 
23:                save updated  $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$  at  $S_{CENTRAL}$ 
24:            end if
25:        end if
26:    end if
27:    if contacted by AgentLauncher for processing the results then
28:        AgentName  $\leftarrow$  retrieve AgentName from AgentProfile
29:        ItinType  $\leftarrow$  retrieve ItinType from incoming  $L^{AgentInfo}$ 
30:        if ItinType = "Parallel" then
31:             $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles} \leftarrow$  load  $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$  from  $S_{CENTRAL}$ 

```

```

32:      dispatch  $L_{AgentName}^{AllProfiles}$  to AgentLauncher
33:    end if
34:  end if
35: end while
36: end procedure
    
```


Figure 1. AeQARM-AAPDB MAS

3.2. Protein Data Bank

AeQARM-AAPDB system is tested on a real dataset of protein sequences, the Astral SCOP [16], [17] version 1.75 genetic domain sequence subsets, based on PDB SEQRES records with less than 40% identity to each other [18]. There are total of 10569 Protein records in this dataset. This single PDB is divided into 3 unites (PDB_1 , PDB_2 and PDB_3) of 3523 protein records in each and are stored at three distributed sites. Each PDB_i is further filtered to generate $FPDB_i$ for PS length range ≥ 50 and ≤ 400 . A total of only 9633 ($3341 (FPDB_1) + 3253 (FPDB_2) + 3039 (FPDB_3)$) such filtered records are considered for the mining. The frequencies of 20 amino acids in each protein sequence are retrieved and stored in AAF_i which is further mapped into BDB_i for

each amino acid having 15 frequency ranges (partitions) resulting into 300 amino acids $\langle attribute, value \rangle$ pairs as shown in Appendix A.4.

3.3. Layout and working of AeQARM-AAPDB system

AeQARM-AAPDB MAS is shown in Figure 1. This MAS consists of total seven agents, clones of six MAs in serial number 1 to 6 are dispatched from $S_{CENTRAL}$ with parallel itinerary migration and one at serial number 7 is an intelligent stationary agent (SA) running at $S_{CENTRAL}$ to perform the different tasks. The CPU time taken by a MA while processing on each site along with some other specific information is carried back in the result bag at $S_{CENTRAL}$. Relationship among these agents and their working behaviour are given as follows.

1. **Protein Data Bank Filtering Agent (PDBFA):** Clones of this MA is dispatched in parallel to each distributed site by AL. It carries the *AgentProfile* along with it and filters PDB_i to generate $FPDB_i$ at each site S_i . PDBFA carries back the computational time ($CPUTime$) at each site S_i and $TripTime_{end}$.
2. **Amino Acids Frequency Finder Agent (AAFFA):** Every clone of this MA carries the *AgentProfile* along with it and finds the frequencies of each amino acids in every protein sequence record in $FPDB_i$ to create AAF_i at each site S_i . AAFFA carries back the computational time ($CPUTime$) at each site S_i and $TripTime_{end}$.
3. **Frequency Mapping and Itemset Data Bank Generater Agent (FMIDBGA):** Every clone of this MA carries the *AgentProfile* and *maxfrq* (the given maximum frequency range for amino acids) along with it. It divides the frequencies of each amino acids in AAF_i into intervals and maps the frequencies into Boolean values to create BDB_i for frequency intervals and further maps it to IDB_i for frequency interval items.
4. **Local Knowledge Generator Agent with Parallel Itinerary (LKGA_P):** Every cloned LKGA_P carries the *AgentProfile*, *min_th_sup* and *min_th_conf* along with it. This agent is embedded with Apriori algorithm [19] for generating all the frequent k-itemset lists. This agent may be equipped with decision making capability to select other FIM algorithms based on the density of the dataset at a particular site. It first performs the FIM to generate and store $L_{k(i)}^{FI}$ and $L_{k(i)}^{FISC}$ at site S_i by scanning the local IDB_i at that site with the constraint of *min_th_sup*. It then performs the ARM applying the constraint of *min_th_conf* to generate and store L_i^{LSAR} by using the $L_{k(i)}^{FI}$ and $L_{k(i)}^{FISC}$. L_i^{LSAR} list also contains support and confidence for a particular association rule along with site name. It carries back the computational time ($CPUTime$) at each site S_i and $TripTime_{end}$.
5. **Local Knowledge Collector Agent with Parallel Itinerary (LKCA_P):** Every cloned LKGA_P carries the *AgentProfile* and collects the list of local frequent k-itemset ($L_{k(i)}^{FI}$) and list of locally strong association rules (L_i^{LSAR}) generated by LKGA_P. It carries back these distributed results in the result bag to RM at $S_{CENTRAL}$ where these results are integrated with the help of a RIA stationary agent. In addition to this resultant knowledge it also carries back the computational time ($CPUTime$) at each site S_i and $TripTime_{end}$.
6. **Global Knowledge Dispatcher Agent with Parallel Itinerary (GKDA_P):** Every cloned GKDA_P carries *AgentProfile* containing global knowledge ($L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR}$) for further

decision making and comparing with local knowledge at that site. It carries back the computational time (CPU_{Time}) at each site S_i and $TripTime_{end}$.

7. **Result Integration and Global Knowledge Generator Agent (RIGKGA)**: It is a stationary agent at $S_{CENTRAL}$, mainly used for processing the result bags of all clones of LKCA_P. It creates a list of total frequent k-itemset (L_k^{TFI}), a list of global frequent itemset, L_k^{GFI} and a list of total locally strong association rules (L^{TLSAR}). L_k^{TFI} and L^{TLSAR} are further processed to generate and store $L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR}$ list.

Figure 2. Control Panel of AeQARM-AAPDB

Table 2. Network Configuration

Site Name	Processor	OS	LAN Configuration	
			IP ^a	Network
$S_{CENTRAL}$	Intel ^b	MS ^c	192.168.46.5	NW ^d
S_1	Intel ^b	MS ^c	192.168.46.212	NW ^d
S_2	Intel ^b	MS ^c	192.168.46.189	NW ^d
S_3	Intel ^b	MS ^c	192.168.46.213	NW ^d

a. IP address with Mask: 255.255.255.0 and Gateway 192.168.46.1
 b. Intel Pentium Dual Core(3.40 GHz, 3.40 GHz) with 512 MB RAM
 c. Microsoft Windows XP Professional ver. 2002
 d. Network Speed: 100 Mbps and Network Adaptor: 82566DM-2 Gigabit NIC

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND PERFORMANCE STUDY

All the agents as well as Control Panel of the system, as shown in Figure 2, are implemented in Java. The required configuration for the deployment of the system is shown in Table 2 with additional deployment of DM_AEE at each distributed site and AL and RM at $S_{CENTRAL}$.

Sr. No.	Strong Association Rules for frequent 2-Itemsets		
	L	AR (support,confidence)	Site
1	[16, 92]	{92} => {16} (23%, 73%)	192.168.46.212
2		{92} => {16} (24%, 66%)	192.168.46.189
3		{92} => {16} (23%, 66%)	192.168.46.213
4	[16, 151]	{16} => {151} (44%, 59%)	192.168.46.212
5		{151} => {16} (44%, 82%)	192.168.46.212
6		{151} => {16} (20%, 72%)	192.168.46.189
7	[16, 152]	{151} => {16} (29%, 64%)	192.168.46.213
8		{152} => {16} (24%, 72%)	192.168.46.212
9		{152} => {16} (23%, 62%)	192.168.46.189
10	[16, 271]	{152} => {16} (25%, 68%)	192.168.46.213
11		{16} => {271} (58%, 79%)	192.168.46.212
12		{271} => {16} (58%, 79%)	192.168.46.212
13	[16, 271]	{16} => {271} (38%, 64%)	192.168.46.189
14		{271} => {16} (38%, 64%)	192.168.46.189
15		{16} => {271} (47%, 73%)	192.168.46.213
16	[16, 287]	{271} => {16} (47%, 67%)	192.168.46.213
17		{287} => {16} (27%, 78%)	192.168.46.212
18		{287} => {16} (20%, 66%)	192.168.46.189
19	[91, 271]	{287} => {16} (24%, 66%)	192.168.46.213
20		{91} => {271} (43%, 82%)	192.168.46.212
21		{271} => {91} (43%, 59%)	192.168.46.212
22	[92, 271]	{91} => {271} (20%, 77%)	192.168.46.189
23		{92} => {271} (23%, 64%)	192.168.46.189
24		{92} => {271} (23%, 67%)	192.168.46.213
25	[151, 271]	{271} => {91} (36%, 52%)	192.168.46.213
26		{92} => {271} (22%, 71%)	192.168.46.212
27		{151} => {271} (20%, 69%)	192.168.46.189
28	[152, 271]	{151} => {271} (37%, 81%)	192.168.46.213
29		{271} => {151} (37%, 53%)	192.168.46.213
30		{152} => {271} (23%, 70%)	192.168.46.212
31	[197, 271]	{152} => {271} (22%, 60%)	192.168.46.189
32		{152} => {271} (24%, 66%)	192.168.46.213
33		{197} => {271} (29%, 80%)	192.168.46.212
34	[271, 287]	{197} => {271} (20%, 73%)	192.168.46.189
35		{197} => {271} (26%, 76%)	192.168.46.213
36		{287} => {271} (27%, 77%)	192.168.46.213
37	[271, 287]	{287} => {271} (22%, 71%)	192.168.46.189
38		{287} => {271} (26%, 75%)	192.168.46.213
39		{287} => {271} (26%, 75%)	192.168.46.213

Figure 7. Globally strong association rules for globally frequent 2-itemsets

Sr. No.	Strong Quantitative Association Rules for 2-Itemsets(amino acids)		
	L	AR (support,confidence)	Site
1	{<C:0..2> <H:3..5>}	{<H:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (23%, 73%)	192.168.46.212
2		{<H:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (24%, 66%)	192.168.46.189
3		{<H:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (23%, 66%)	192.168.46.213
4	{<C:0..2> <M:0..2>}	{<C:0..2> => {<M:0..2>} (44%, 59%)	192.168.46.212
5		{<M:0..2> => {<C:0..2>} (44%, 82%)	192.168.46.212
6		{<M:0..2> => {<C:0..2>} (20%, 72%)	192.168.46.189
7	{<C:0..2> <M:3..5>}	{<M:0..2> => {<C:0..2>} (29%, 64%)	192.168.46.213
8		{<M:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (24%, 72%)	192.168.46.212
9		{<M:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (23%, 62%)	192.168.46.189
10	{<C:0..2> <W:0..2>}	{<M:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (25%, 68%)	192.168.46.213
11		{<C:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (58%, 79%)	192.168.46.212
12		{<W:0..2> => {<C:0..2>} (58%, 79%)	192.168.46.212
13	{<C:0..2> <Y:3..5>}	{<C:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (38%, 64%)	192.168.46.189
14		{<W:0..2> => {<C:0..2>} (38%, 66%)	192.168.46.213
15		{<C:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (47%, 73%)	192.168.46.213
16	{<C:0..2> <Y:3..5>}	{<W:0..2> => {<C:0..2>} (47%, 67%)	192.168.46.213
17		{<Y:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (27%, 78%)	192.168.46.212
18		{<Y:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (20%, 66%)	192.168.46.189
19	{<H:0..2> <W:0..2>}	{<Y:3..5> => {<C:0..2>} (24%, 68%)	192.168.46.213
20		{<H:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (43%, 82%)	192.168.46.212
21		{<W:0..2> => {<H:0..2>} (43%, 59%)	192.168.46.212
22	{<H:0..2> <W:0..2>}	{<H:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (20%, 77%)	192.168.46.189
23		{<H:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (36%, 83%)	192.168.46.213
24		{<W:0..2> => {<H:0..2>} (36%, 52%)	192.168.46.213
25	{<H:3..5> <W:0..2>}	{<H:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (22%, 71%)	192.168.46.212
26		{<H:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (23%, 64%)	192.168.46.189
27		{<H:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (23%, 67%)	192.168.46.213
28	{<M:0..2> <W:0..2>}	{<M:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (43%, 80%)	192.168.46.212
29		{<W:0..2> => {<M:0..2>} (43%, 59%)	192.168.46.212
30		{<M:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (20%, 69%)	192.168.46.189
31	{<M:0..2> <W:0..2>}	{<M:0..2> => {<W:0..2>} (37%, 81%)	192.168.46.213
32		{<W:0..2> => {<M:0..2>} (37%, 53%)	192.168.46.213
33		{<M:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (23%, 70%)	192.168.46.212
34	{<M:3..5> <W:0..2>}	{<M:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (22%, 60%)	192.168.46.189
35		{<M:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (24%, 66%)	192.168.46.213
36		{<Q:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (29%, 80%)	192.168.46.212
37	{<Q:3..5> <W:0..2>}	{<Q:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (20%, 73%)	192.168.46.189
38		{<Q:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (26%, 76%)	192.168.46.213
39		{<Y:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (27%, 77%)	192.168.46.212
40	{<W:0..2> <Y:3..5>}	{<Y:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (22%, 71%)	192.168.46.189
41		{<Y:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (26%, 75%)	192.168.46.213
41		{<Y:3..5> => {<W:0..2>} (26%, 75%)	192.168.46.213

Figure 8. Globally strong association rules for frequent 2- amino acids

$L_{k(1)}^{FI}$ and $L_{k(1)}^{FISC}$ at site S_1 generated by LKGA_P agent with 20% *min_th_sup* are shown in Appendix B.1. Locally strong association rules (L_1^{LSAR}) generated by LKGA_P for frequent item numbers at site S_1 are shown in Appendix B.2 and the same for their corresponding amino acids frequency range are shown in Appendix B.3. Globally strong association rules ($L_{CENTRAL}^{GSAR}$) for the globally frequent itemsets generated by RIGKGA are shown in Figure 7. When these item numbers are mapped with their corresponding amino acids frequency ranges then globally strong

quantitative association rules for frequent 2 amino acids are obtained and shown in Figure 8. The results, as shown in Figure 8, reveals that:

- < Cysteine: 0..2 > is strongly associated with < Histidine: 3..5 >, < Methionine:0..2 >, < Methionine: 3..5 >, < Tryptophan: 0..2 >, and < Tyrosine..3::5 >
- < Tryptophan: 0..2 > is strongly associated with < Histidine: 0..2 >, <Histidine: 3..5 >, < Methionine: 0..2 >, < Methionine: 3..5 >, < Glutamine: 3..5 > and < Tyrosine: 3..5 >

5. CONCLUSION

Mobile agents strongly qualify for designing distributed applications. DDM, when clubbed with the agent technology, makes a promising alliance that gives favourable results and provides a rewarding solution in managing Big Data with ever increasing size. In this study, a MAS called AeQARM-AAPDB to mine the strong quantitative association rules among amino acids present in primary structure of the proteins from the distributed proteins data sets using intelligent agents is presented. Such globally strong association rules are used in understanding of protein composition and are desirable for synthesis of artificial proteins. Agent-based bio-data mining leaves the technical details of choosing mining algorithms, forming hybrid system, and preparing specific data format to the intelligent system itself because such requirements are unreasonable for most biologists. It alleviates the technical difficulty while enhance the reusability of the mining algorithms and available datasets. By applying multi-agent based distributed bio-data mining, the computing load can be balanced and the computational effort can be achieved in a parallel and scalable manner.

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AUTHORS

Gurpreet Singh Bhamra is currently working as Assistant Professor at Department of Computer Science and Engineering, M. M. University, Mullana, Haryana. He received his B.Sc. (Computer Sc.) and MCA from Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra in 1995 and 1998, respectively. He is pursuing Ph.D. from Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Thapar University, Patiala, Punjab. He is in teaching since 1998. He has published 12 research papers in International/National Journals and International Conferences. He is a Life Member of Computer Society of India. His research interests are in Distributed Computing, Distributed Data Mining, Mobile Agents and Bio-informatics.

Dr. Anil Kumar Verma is currently working as Associate Professor at Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Thapar University, Patiala. He received his B.S., M.S. and Ph.D. in 1991, 2001 and 2008 respectively, majoring in Computer science and engineering. He has worked as Lecturer at M.M.M. Engineering College, Gorakhpur from 1991 to 1996. He joined Thapar Institute of Engineering & Technology in 1996 as a Systems Analyst in the Computer Centre and is presently associated with the same Institute. He has been a visiting faculty to many institutions. He has published over 100 papers in referred journals and conferences (India and Abroad). He is a MISCI (Turkey), LMCSI (Mumbai), GMAIMA (New Delhi). He is a certified software quality auditor by MoCIT, Govt. of India. His research interests include wireless networks, routing algorithms and securing ad hoc networks and data mining.


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>d1dlwa_ a.1.1.1 (A:) Protozoan/bacterial hemoglobin (Ciliate (Paramecium caudatum) [TaxId: 5885])#slfeqlg
>d1s69a_ a.1.1.1 (A:) Protozoan/bacterial hemoglobin (Cyanobacteria (Synechocystis sp.), pcc 6803 [TaxId: :
>d1ldra_ a.1.1.1 (A:) Protozoan/bacterial hemoglobin (Mycobacterium tuberculosis, HbN [TaxId: 1773])#gllsr.
>dingka_ a.1.1.1 (A:) Protozoan/bacterial hemoglobin (Mycobacterium tuberculosis, HbO [TaxId: 1773])#ksfydr.
>d1ux8a_ a.1.1.1 (A:) Protozoan/bacterial hemoglobin (Bacillus subtilis [TaxId: 1423])#napyeaige1lsglvdtf.
>d1kr7a_ a.1.1.4 (A:) Nerve tissue mini-hemoglobin (neural globin) (Milky ribbon-worm (Cerebratulus lacteus
>d3sdha_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Hemoglobin I (Ark clam (Scapharca inaequivalvis) [TaxId: 6561])#svydaaq1tdyvkklrdsi
>d1h0ba_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Hemoglobin I (Clam (Lucina pectinata) [TaxId: 29163])#slsaaqkdnvkswakasaawgtagpeffm
>d1h97a_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Trematode hemoglobin/myoglobin (Paramphistomum epiclitum [TaxId: 54403])#t1ckheqdilll
>d1j17a_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Glycera globin (Marine bloodworm (Glycera dibranchiata) [TaxId: 6350])#glsaaqrqvast
>d1a6ma_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Myoglobin (Sperm whale (Physeter catodon) [TaxId: 9755])#vlsegvqlvlnvkvadavaghgqd.
>d1mbaa_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Myoglobin (Slug sea hare (Aplysia limacina) [TaxId: 6502])#slsaaeadlagkswapvfanknang.
>d1ecda_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Erythrocyruorin (Midge (Chironomus thummi thummi), fraction III [TaxId: 7154])#lsadqis.
>d2gdma_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Leghemoglobin (Yellow lupin (Lupinus luteus) [TaxId: 3873])#galtesqaalvkssweefnanipkl ****
>d1cg5a_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Hemoglobin, alpha-chain (Cartilaginous fish akaei (Dasyatis akajei) [TaxId: 31902])#v
>d3d1ka1 a.1.1.2 (A:1-142) Hemoglobin, alpha-chain (Antarctic fish (Trematomus newnesi) [TaxId: 35730])#sl:
>d1cg5b_ a.1.1.2 (B:) Hemoglobin, beta-chain (Cartilaginous fish akaei (Dasyatis akajei) [TaxId: 31902])#vl
>d3d1kb1 a.1.1.2 (B:1-146) Hemoglobin, beta-chain (Antarctic fish (Trematomus newnesi) [TaxId: 35730])#vew
>d1gcvb_ a.1.1.2 (B:) Hemoglobin, beta-chain (Houndshark (Mustelus griseus) [TaxId: 89020])#vhwvqeerdeiskt.
>d1it2a_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Hagfish hemoglobin (Inshore hagfish (Eptatretus burgeri) [TaxId: 7764])#p1idqgp1ptlt.
>d1asha_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Ascaris hemoglobin, domain 1 (Pig roundworm (Ascaris suum) [TaxId: 6253])#fankrrelcmk.
>d1itha_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Hemoglobin (Innkeeper worm (Urechis caupo) [TaxId: 6431])#gltaaqikaigqhwfinkqclqaas
>d1h1ba_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Hemoglobin, different isoforms (Caudina arenicola, also known as Molpadia arenicola
>d1q1fa_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Neuroglobin (Mouse (Mus musculus) [TaxId: 10090])#rpeselirgswrvvsrplehgtvifar1alep.
>d1cqxal a.1.1.2 (A:1-150) Flavohemoglobin, N-terminal domain (Alcaligenes eutrophus [TaxId: 106590])#mltq.
>d2qfka1 a.1.1.2 (A:1-137) Dehaloperoxidase (Amphitrite ornata [TaxId: 129555])#gfkqdiatirgdrtyaqd1af1fln.
>d1or4a_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Heme-based aerotactic transducer HemA_T, sensor domain (Bacillus subtilis [TaxId: 142:
>d1urva_ a.1.1.2 (A:) Cytoglobin (Human (Homo sapiens) [TaxId: 9606])#elseaerkavqamwarlyansedvqvailrvffvnfj

```

A.3 AAF₁ generated from FPDB₁ at site S₁

Each column heading represents single letter code of an amino acid. Each row represents the frequencies of amino acids in a particular protein sequence record.

S. N.	a	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	k	l	m	n	p	q	r	s	t	v	w	y
1)	22	1	3	4	6	11	2	3	2	8	2	8	2	8	3	3	12	14	1	1
2)	17	0	12	10	6	9	6	2	9	12	3	3	2	4	6	1	6	10	0	5
3)	14	0	6	8	6	13	5	8	5	12	3	1	6	4	6	8	7	12	0	3
4)	13	1	10	12	6	6	5	4	2	12	4	1	5	3	15	8	4	7	2	6
5)	9	1	5	12	6	7	6	4	4	16	4	3	9	5	8	4	7	4	1	4
6)	21	2	7	3	5	12	6	4	9	8	1	6	2	3	2	6	2	6	1	4
7)	18	1	12	3	6	10	2	8	15	13	3	10	2	6	4	7	6	13	2	4
8)	28	1	8	5	10	16	2	2	11	9	6	6	3	5	2	11	5	7	4	1
9)	14	0	6	14	7	8	11	10	14	11	5	3	5	5	3	6	11	9	0	5
10)	27	1	6	8	4	21	5	7	11	10	5	3	3	4	3	12	1	11	2	3
11)	17	0	7	14	6	10	12	9	19	18	2	1	4	4	4	6	5	8	2	3
12)	29	0	8	5	15	11	1	4	11	11	3	9	6	2	4	13	2	10	2	0
13)	17	0	9	5	14	11	4	9	10	6	4	5	5	4	3	9	9	9	1	2
14)	21	0	6	14	7	7	5	9	14	14	1	6	5	4	1	9	8	17	3	2
15)	17	4	7	10	8	5	10	3	10	20	1	9	3	4	4	6	6	10	1	3
16)	13	1	9	5	5	8	5	10	14	14	4	4	7	2	5	14	5	11	2	4
17)	12	0	8	9	9	7	7	6	15	14	1	5	2	10	5	6	6	12	2	5
18)	15	2	12	5	7	10	7	9	9	13	5	7	3	4	4	10	7	9	2	6
19)	7	2	15	5	9	5	8	9	12	9	3	1	3	7	6	6	10	12	3	4
20)	6	2	8	10	10	4	2	17	18	13	1	7	7	8	2	13	5	7	2	4

A.4 Amino acids frequency ranges (15 ranges for each amino acid)

Item No. column represents Serial No. from 1 to 300. Data in the AA Frequency Range column represents single letter code of amino acid along with a frequency range. Frequency of each amino acid is divided into 15 partitions (ranges) resulting into 300 items for 20 amino acids. For example if frequency of amino acid Alanine (A) in a protein record is 22 it lies at Item No. 8.

Item No.	AA Frequency Range								
1	<A:0..2>	61	<F:0..2>	121	<K:0..2>	181	<P:0..2>	241	<T:0..2>
2	<A:3..5>	62	<F:3..5>	122	<K:3..5>	182	<P:3..5>	242	<T:3..5>
3	<A:6..8>	63	<F:6..8>	123	<K:6..8>	183	<P:6..8>	243	<T:6..8>
4	<A:9..11>	64	<F:9..11>	124	<K:9..11>	184	<P:9..11>	244	<T:9..11>
5	<A:12..14>	65	<F:12..14>	125	<K:12..14>	185	<P:12..14>	245	<T:12..14>
6	<A:15..17>	66	<F:15..17>	126	<K:15..17>	186	<P:15..17>	246	<T:15..17>
7	<A:18..20>	67	<F:18..20>	127	<K:18..20>	187	<P:18..20>	247	<T:18..20>
8	<A:21..30>	68	<F:21..30>	128	<K:21..30>	188	<P:21..30>	248	<T:21..30>
9	<A:31..40>	69	<F:31..40>	129	<K:31..40>	189	<P:31..40>	249	<T:31..40>
10	<A:41..50>	70	<F:41..50>	130	<K:41..50>	190	<P:41..50>	250	<T:41..50>
11	<A:51..60>	71	<F:51..60>	131	<K:51..60>	191	<P:51..60>	251	<T:51..60>
12	<A:61..70>	72	<F:61..70>	132	<K:61..70>	192	<P:61..70>	252	<T:61..70>
13	<A:71..80>	73	<F:71..80>	133	<K:71..80>	193	<P:71..80>	253	<T:71..80>
14	<A:81..90>	74	<F:81..90>	134	<K:81..90>	194	<P:81..90>	254	<T:81..90>
15	<A:91..400>	75	<F:91..400>	135	<K:91..400>	195	<P:91..400>	255	<T:91..400>

⋮

A.5 BDB_1 at site S_1

This Boolean data bank (BDB_1) is created using AAF_1 as shown in Appendix A.3 and amino acids frequency range table as shown in Appendix A.4. Each column heading represents an Item No. as shown in Appendix A.4. Each amino acid has 15 frequency partitions and for each amino acid, a boolean value '1' is put under that Item No. in which frequency of amino acid lies in a particular protein record otherwise a value '0' is considered. For example it clear from AAF_1 that the frequency of amino acid Alanine (A) in the 1st protein record is 22 and this frequency lies at Item No. 8 in frequency range table as shown in Appendix A.4, so a boolean value '1' is put under Item No. 8 in the 1st protein record in BDB_1 .

S.No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
1)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2)	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7)	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11)	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13)	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15)	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18)	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19)	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20)	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23)	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28)	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29)	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

⋮

A.6 IDB_1 at site S_1

This Itemset data bank (IDB_1) is created using BDB_1 as shown in Appendix A.4. Each record in this dataset consist of 20 Item Numbers, one for each of amino acids for which a boolean value '1' is stored in BDB_1 .

1)	8	16	32	47	63	79	91	107	121	138	151	168	181	198	212	227	245	260	271	286
2)	6	16	35	49	63	79	93	106	124	140	152	167	181	197	213	226	243	259	271	287
3)	5	16	33	48	63	80	92	108	122	140	152	166	183	197	213	228	243	260	271	287
4)	5	16	34	50	63	78	92	107	121	140	152	166	182	197	216	228	242	258	271	288
5)	4	16	32	50	63	78	93	107	122	141	152	167	184	197	213	227	243	257	271	287
6)	8	16	33	47	62	80	93	107	124	138	151	168	181	197	211	228	241	258	271	287
7)	7	16	35	47	63	79	91	108	126	140	152	169	181	198	212	228	243	260	271	287
8)	8	16	33	47	64	81	91	106	124	139	153	168	182	197	211	229	242	258	272	286
9)	5	16	33	50	63	78	94	109	125	139	152	167	182	197	212	228	244	259	271	287
10)	8	16	33	48	62	83	92	108	124	139	152	167	182	197	212	230	241	259	271	287
11)	6	16	33	50	63	79	95	109	127	142	151	166	182	197	212	228	242	258	271	287
12)	8	16	33	47	66	79	91	107	124	139	152	169	183	196	212	230	241	259	271	286
13)	6	16	34	47	65	79	92	109	124	138	152	167	182	197	212	229	244	259	271	286
14)	8	16	33	50	63	78	92	109	125	140	151	168	182	197	211	229	243	261	272	286
15)	6	17	33	49	63	77	94	107	124	142	151	169	182	197	212	228	243	259	271	287
16)	5	16	34	47	62	78	92	109	125	140	152	167	183	196	212	230	242	259	271	287
17)	5	16	33	49	64	78	93	108	126	140	151	167	181	199	212	228	243	260	271	287
18)	6	16	35	47	63	79	93	109	124	140	152	168	182	197	212	229	243	259	271	288
19)	3	16	36	47	64	77	93	109	125	139	152	166	182	198	213	228	244	260	272	287
20)	3	16	33	49	64	77	91	111	127	140	151	168	183	198	211	230	242	258	271	287

APPENDIX B – RESULTANT KNOWLEDGE OF AEQARM-AAPDB SYSTEM

B.1 $L_{k(1)}^{FI}$ and $L_{k(1)}^{FISC}$ at site S_1

List of frequent k-itemset, i.e., $L_{k(1)}^{FI}$ is represented by column **L** and column **SC** shows the support count of the corresponding frequent k-itemset, i.e., $L_{k(1)}^{FISC}$ at site S_1 . These frequent itemsets and their support counts are obtained by processing the Itemset Data Bank (IDB_1) as shown in Appendix A.6.

Sr. No.	1-Itemsets		2-Itemsets		3-Itemsets		4-Itemsets	
	L	SC	L	SC	L	SC	L	SC
1	[2]	713	[16, 32]	852	[16, 32, 271]	735	[16, 91, 151, 271]	869
2	[3]	765	[16, 33]	731	[16, 61, 271]	736		
3	[16]	2508	[16, 48]	769	[16, 62, 271]	757		
4	[32]	1015	[16, 61]	838	[16, 91, 151]	998		
5	[33]	923	[16, 62]	933	[16, 91, 271]	1252		
6	[48]	955	[16, 91]	1473	[16, 91, 286]	670		
7	[49]	695	[16, 92]	784	[16, 107, 271]	691		
8	[61]	948	[16, 107]	831	[16, 151, 271]	1239		
9	[62]	1172	[16, 108]	684	[16, 167, 271]	778		
10	[77]	796	[16, 123]	693	[16, 182, 271]	769		
11	[78]	849	[16, 151]	1492	[16, 197, 271]	800		
12	[91]	1769	[16, 152]	811	[16, 212, 271]	728		
13	[92]	1073	[16, 166]	690	[16, 227, 271]	680		
14	[107]	1010	[16, 167]	918	[16, 242, 271]	724		
15	[108]	870	[16, 181]	674	[16, 271, 286]	826		
16	[122]	767	[16, 182]	917	[16, 271, 287]	750		
17	[123]	874	[16, 197]	980	[91, 151, 271]	999		
18	[138]	708	[16, 212]	859	[91, 271, 286]	672		
19	[139]	682	[16, 213]	679				
20	[151]	1813	[16, 227]	766				
21	[152]	1112	[16, 242]	836				
22	[166]	781	[16, 271]	1961				
23	[167]	1145	[16, 286]	952				
24	[168]	747	[16, 287]	932				
25	[181]	733	[32, 91]	670				

⋮

B.2 L_1^{LSAR} for Item numbers at site S_1

Column **L** represents frequent k-itemset and column **AR(support,confidence)** shows the list of locally strong association rules, i.e., L_1^{LSAR} at site S_1 . Each strong rule has its associated support and confidence factor. The minimum threshold support is taken as 20% and minimum threshold confidence as 50% for generating the strong rules by making use of the data as shown in Appendix B.1.

Sr. No.	Strong ARs for Frequent 4-itemsets		Strong ARs for Frequent 3-itemsets		Strong ARs for Frequent 2-itemsets	
	L	AR(support,confidence)	L	AR(support,confidence)	L	AR(support,confidence)
1	[16, 91, 151, 271]	[16, 91] => [151, 271] (26%, 58%)	[16, 32, 271]	[32] => [16, 271] (21%, 72%)	[16, 32]	[32] => [16] (25%, 83%)
2		[16, 151] => [91, 271] (26%, 58%)		[16, 32] => [271] (21%, 86%)	[16, 33]	[33] => [16] (21%, 79%)
3		[91, 151] => [16, 271] (26%, 74%)		[32, 271] => [16] (21%, 84%)	[16, 48]	[48] => [16] (23%, 80%)
4		[91, 271] => [16, 151] (26%, 59%)	[61] => [16, 271] (22%, 77%)	[16, 61]	[61] => [16] (25%, 88%)	
5		[151, 271] => [16, 91] (26%, 59%)	[16, 61] => [271] (22%, 87%)	[16, 62]	[62] => [16] (27%, 79%)	
6		[16, 91, 151] => [271] (26%, 87%)	[61, 271] => [16] (22%, 89%)	[16, 91]	[16] => [91] (44%, 58%)	
7		[16, 91, 271] => [151] (26%, 69%)	[62] => [16, 271] (22%, 64%)	[91]	[91] => [16] (44%, 83%)	
8		[16, 151, 271] => [91] (26%, 70%)	[16, 62] => [271] (22%, 81%)	[16, 92]	[92] => [16] (23%, 73%)	
9		[91, 151, 271] => [16] (26%, 86%)	[62, 271] => [16] (22%, 81%)	[16, 107]	[107] => [16] (24%, 82%)	
10		[91] => [16, 151] (29%, 56%)	[16, 108]	[108] => [16] (20%, 78%)		
11		[151] => [16, 91] (29%, 55%)	[16, 123]	[123] => [16] (20%, 79%)		
12		[16, 91] => [151] (29%, 67%)	[16]	[16] => [151] (44%, 59%)		
13		[16, 151] => [91] (29%, 66%)	[16, 151]	[151] => [16] (44%, 82%)		
14		[91, 151] => [16] (29%, 85%)	[16, 152]	[152] => [16] (24%, 72%)		
15		[91] => [16, 271] (37%, 70%)	[16, 166]	[166] => [16] (20%, 88%)		
16		[271] => [16, 91] (37%, 50%)	[16, 167]	[167] => [16] (27%, 80%)		
17		[16, 91] => [271] (37%, 84%)	[16, 181]	[181] => [16] (20%, 91%)		
18		[16, 271] => [91] (37%, 63%)	[16, 182]	[182] => [16] (27%, 79%)		
19		[91, 271] => [16] (37%, 85%)	[16, 197]	[197] => [16] (29%, 80%)		
20		[286] => [16, 91] (20%, 60%)	[16, 212]	[212] => [16] (25%, 81%)		
21		[16, 286] => [91] (20%, 70%)	[16, 213]	[213] => [16] (20%, 76%)		
22		[91, 286] => [16] (20%, 88%)	[16, 227]	[227] => [16] (22%, 86%)		
23		[107] => [16, 271] (20%, 68%)	[16, 242]	[242] => [16] (25%, 82%)		
24		[16, 107] => [271] (20%, 83%)	[16]	[16] => [271] (58%, 78%)		
25		[107, 271] => [16] (20%, 83%)	[16, 271]	[271] => [16] (58%, 79%)		

⋮

B.3 L_1^{LSAR} for corresponding Amino acid frequency ranges at site S_1

Replace Item No. in Appendix B.2 data with its corresponding Amino acid frequency range as shown in table Appendix A.4.

Sr. No.	Strong ARs for Frequent 4-itemsets		Strong ARs for Frequent 3-itemsets	
	L	AR(support,confidence)	L	AR(support,confidence)
1	{ <C.0.2> <H.0.2> }	{ <C.0.2> <H.0.2> } => { <M.0.2> <W.0.2> } (26%, 58%)	{ <C.0.2> <D.3.5> <W.0.2> }	{ <D.3.5> } => { <C.0.2> <W.0.2> } (21%, 72%)
2		{ <C.0.2> <M.0.2> } => { <H.0.2> <W.0.2> } (26%, 58%)		{ <C.0.2> <D.3.5> } => { <W.0.2> } (21%, 86%)
3		{ <H.0.2> <M.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <W.0.2> } (26%, 74%)		{ <D.3.5> <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (21%, 84%)
4		{ <H.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <M.0.2> } (26%, 59%)	{ <F.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <W.0.2> } (22%, 77%)	
5		{ <M.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <H.0.2> } (26%, 59%)	{ <C.0.2> <F.0.2> } => { <W.0.2> } (22%, 87%)	
6		{ <C.0.2> <H.0.2> <M.0.2> } => { <W.0.2> } (26%, 87%)	{ <F.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (22%, 89%)	
7		{ <C.0.2> <H.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <M.0.2> } (26%, 69%)	{ <F.3.5> } => { <C.0.2> <W.0.2> } (22%, 64%)	
8		{ <C.0.2> <M.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <H.0.2> } (26%, 70%)	{ <C.0.2> <F.3.5> } => { <W.0.2> } (22%, 81%)	
9		{ <H.0.2> <M.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (26%, 86%)	{ <F.3.5> <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (22%, 81%)	
10		{ <H.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <M.0.2> } (29%, 56%)		
11		{ <M.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <H.0.2> } (29%, 55%)		
12		{ <C.0.2> <H.0.2> } => { <M.0.2> } (29%, 67%)		
13		{ <C.0.2> <M.0.2> } => { <H.0.2> } (29%, 66%)		
14		{ <H.0.2> <M.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (29%, 85%)		
15		{ <H.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <W.0.2> } (37%, 70%)		
16		{ <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <H.0.2> } (37%, 50%)		
17		{ <C.0.2> <H.0.2> } => { <W.0.2> } (37%, 84%)		
18		{ <C.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <H.0.2> } (37%, 63%)		
19		{ <H.0.2> <W.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (37%, 85%)		
20		{ <Y.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> <H.0.2> } (20%, 60%)		
21		{ <C.0.2> <H.0.2> <Y.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (20%, 70%)		
22		{ <H.0.2> <Y.0.2> } => { <C.0.2> } (20%, 88%)		

⋮